

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-178-ODH-1% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230307
Vial:	30	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 2 178
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	276.0nm
Run Time:	18.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 276.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/7/2023 8:21:09 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 11:29:36 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.896	4029748	46.74	297552
2	8.418	4078703	47.31	284726
3	9.137	259500	3.01	16308
4	14.743	253433	2.94	11178

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-180-ODH-1% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230307
Vial:	31	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	4
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	276.0nm
Run Time:	18.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 276.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/7/2023 8:39:48 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 3:41:35 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.643	41077	1.65	1246
2	8.553	2442923	98.26	173970
3	9.291	1863	0.07	205
4	14.811	425	0.02	86